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Historical Sciences

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GAS INDUSTRY IN THE RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article examines the development of the gas industry in Russia, which is an important factor of social development that affects the technological structure of the economy, scientific and technological progress, the growth of labor productivity and income of the population. Providing energy is the basis for the development of civilization on Earth. In general, the fuel and energy complex is one of the driving forces of socio-economic development. Based on the importance of the gas industry for the socio-economic development of the country, it is important to ensure the stable functioning of this industry and its further development on the basis of increasing the efficiency of economic activity and increasing investment attractiveness. In this regard, the article pays special attention to the historical and economic analysis and scientific understanding of the development of the gas industry, its place and role in the socio-economic development of the country and individual regions. The reform of the socio-economic system in Russia, profound changes in industry and management systems have an impact on the entire spectrum of socio-economic relations, including sectoral economic systems. Solving the problem of increasing the efficiency of the gas industry involves studying both the internal mechanisms of its progressive movement and ways of effective reform.

Keywords: gas, industry, country, society, industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

At the present stage, the gas industry is one of the most important elements of the economy of the Russian Federation, the further economic development of the country depends on the reliable operation of this industry. To date, the share of gas in the fuel balance of Russian thermal power plants is 62%, and in the European part - 86%. Industry provides about 10% of national GDP, up to 25% of revenues to the state budget of the country. Natural gas exports bring Russia about 15% of foreign exchange earnings. In the next decade, gas demand is projected to grow, which will exceed the growth in demand for other energy sources. This will have a positive impact on the position of Russia, which intends to make gas its main trump card in energy exports, as well as a powerful lever in international politics. Russia ranks first in the world in terms of the volume of explored deposits. Russia accounts for 30% of the total volume of the planet's natural gas.

At the current level of production, this will be enough for 81 years. A unique situation has developed in the Russian gas industry - all state functions have actually been transferred to one of the subjects of economic activity - Gazprom, the activity of the state is limited to regulating gas prices within the country. Gazprom controls 60% of Russia's gas reserves. It accounts for 84% of all-Russian gas production and almost 100% of transportation. The remaining 16% of gas production is carried out by oil companies and independent gas producers. The share of independent producers in the total volume of gas production in Russia is about 7%. At the same time, Gazprom is an instrument of state policy, sometimes even to the detriment of its own economic interests and development.

II. METHODOLOGY

The theoretical and methodological bases of the research is the methods of comparative and institutional analysis, a systematic approach to the study of economic phenomena. The work used domestic and foreign economic literature; legislative and regulatory acts in the field of regulation of natural gas markets in the Russian Federation and the EU; official statistical reporting; research of international organizations; information materials of foreign gas companies; publications of domestic media.

III. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In 1956, the gas industry separated from the oil industry and became an independent branch of the national economy. In connection with the high rates of development of the national economy, the increase in the cost of additionally involved in the balance of fuel and energy resources, the acceleration of the development of nuclear energy, the creation of fuel and energy trunk transport systems at a qualitatively new technical level, the growing influence of the environmental factor, Soviet scientists required research and development of scientifically - economic concepts of long-term development of the domestic gas industry. And they were fulfilled. In the middle of 1960s. fundamentally new systems for the development of gas and gas condensate fields, including Western Siberia, a new technology for the transportation of natural gases and their use were created. For example, the principles of developing gas and gas condensate fields in Western Siberia made it possible to accelerate the commissioning of fields in the northern regions of the Tyumen region - Medvezhya Urengoy, located in difficult natural and climatic conditions, in the permafrost zone. At the same time, the development of fields with an annual production of 100-200 billion m³ of gas required the introduction, for the first time in world practice, of advanced designs of multilayer pipes, the use of which for the construction of gas pipelines ensured high economic efficiency. At the same time, the fuel and energy complex in relation to its one of the main components - the extraction of natural gases - should be considered in conjunction with the further development of the Unified Gas Supply System of the country based on proven and forecast gas reserves.

The studies and feasibility studies carried out in our country served as the basis for drawing up numerous options for the sequence of development of gas and gas condensate fields with different levels of explored reserves throughout the USSR. This made it possible, when developing five-year and long-term plans, to ensure a rational choice of the most efficient gas producing regions, taking into account the sequence and pace of transferring probable reserves into explored ones, putting deposits into experimental development with their simultaneous additional exploration, new technological principles for the construction of gas pipelines, as well as ensuring the rational distribution of gas between by various categories of consumers, depending on the efficiency of using gas as a raw material and fuel. Based on an analysis of the development of the national economy for the eleventh and twelfth five years, it was established that the country's full supply of fuel in the short term depended to a greater extent on the accelerated pace of development of the gas industry.

At the same time, the location of the country's fuel-producing bases and industrial complexes developed in such a way that the European part of the USSR and the Urals did not fully meet their needs for primary fuel and energy resources. In this regard, it was found that, despite the measures taken in the USSR to move energy-intensive industries to the east and the relative increase in connection with this the role of the eastern regions in the all-Union consumption of fuel and energy, the absolute gap in production and the need for fuel in the European part of the country did not lead to the reduction.

This is mainly due to the fact that due to the gradual depletion in the European part of the USSR and in the Urals of industrial reserves of gas, oil and coal (at technically possible at the given level of technological development and economically feasible depths of development), the main increases in fuel production were covered by the eastern regions of the country.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that in the near future, the real factor is the need to transfer significant amounts of fuel over long distances - from east to west. First of all, this provision applies to the gas industry, the further accelerated development of which will take place in exceptionally difficult natural-climatic, economic-geographical and geological-technical conditions, which will inevitably affect the specific cost indicators of exploration and development of gas fields. In this regard, it should be emphasized that only scientific and technological progress can resist these rising prices, both in the field of preparing new industrial reserves, and in relation to the development of deposits, transportation and use of natural gases.

Therefore, at the present stage, the question of the need for a radical technical re-equipment of the gas industry based on the creation of qualitatively new methods of field exploration (completion of the development of direct geophysical and other methods, methods of directed search for pure gas fields, ultrasonic, electro-hydraulic, capsular explosive, etc.) creation of progressive methods of field development, gas transportation.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ГАЗОВОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается развитие газовой отрасли в России, которая является важным фактором общественного развития, влияющим на технологическую структуру экономики, научно-технический прогресс, рост производительности труда и доходов населения. Обеспечение энергией это - основа развития цивилизации на Земле. В целом топливно-энергетический комплекс является одной из движущих сил социально-экономического развития. Исходя из значения газовой отрасли для социально-экономического развития страны, важно обеспечить стабильное функционирование данной отрасли и ее дальнейшее развитие на основе повышения эффективности хозяйственной деятельности и увеличения инвестиционной привлекательности. В связи с этим в статье особое внимание уделяется историко-экономическому анализу и научному осмыслению развития газовой отрасли, ее места и роли в социально-экономическом развитии страны и отдельных регионов. Реформирование социально-экономической системы в России, глубокие изменения в промышленности, системах управления оказывают влияние на весь спектр социально-экономических отношений, в том числе на отраслевые экономические системы. Решение проблемы повышения эффективности газовой отрасли предполагает изучение как внутренних механизмов ее поступательного движения, так и путей эффективного реформирования.

Ключевые слова: газ, отрасль, страна, общество, промышленность.

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